

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan

WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion

Authors: Dimitrios Petalios, CREVIS SPRL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821964.

BEACON

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© BEACON Consortium, 2019

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Content

Table of Content	4
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	5
List of Acronyms.....	7
Executive summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. The BEACON project	10
1.2. The BEACON project objectives	10
2. BEACON Dissemination strategy.....	12
2.1. Dissemination objectives	12
2.2. Dissemination strategy	12
2.3. The BEACON ecosystem.....	13
2.4. BEACON engagement strategy	14
2.4.1. Target audiences & interest in BEACON	15
2.4.2. BEACON Lighthouse customers	17
2.4.3. Agl Enablers – BEACON Advisory Board.....	18
3. BEACON Communication	18
3.1. BEACON communication strategy	18
3.2. Communication tools.....	19
3.2.1. BEACON visual identity	19
3.2.1.1. BEACON logo.....	19
3.2.2. BEACON Templates.....	20
3.2.2.1. BEACON presentation templates.....	20
3.2.2.2. BEACON deliverables template.....	22
3.2.3. BEACON online presence	24
3.2.3.1. BEACON website	24
3.2.4. BEACON Social media.....	24
3.2.4.1. BEACON Facebook page.....	25
3.2.4.2. BEACON LinkedIn Group	26
3.2.4.3. BEACON Twitter account	27

Figure 8. BEACON’s Facebook page 26

Figure 9. BEACON LinkedIn group..... 27

Figure 10. BEACON Twitter account 28

Figure 11. BEACON Newsletter template 29

Figure 12. Subscription to BEACON newsletters (call to action button-Head)..... 31

Figure 13 Subscription to BEACON newsletters (call to action button-footer) 31

Figure 14. BEACON one pager 32

Figure 15. BEACON Brochure 33

Figure 16. BEACON press release..... 34

Figure 17. BEACON project kick-off press release 37

Figure 18. Timeline of DEC activities..... 42

List of Acronyms

Acronyms	Explanation
AB	Advisory Board
AgI	Agricultural Insurance
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DG AGRI	Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG ENV	Directorate General for Environment
DG GROW	Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
EUROGEOSS	European part on Global Earth Observation System of Systems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GEOGLAM	Group on Earth Observations Global Agricultural Monitoring
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Center
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-governmental organization
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PR	Press Release
REA	Research Executive Agency
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UA	Underwriting Agency
WB	World Bank
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The BEACON project aims to develop and commercialize a toolbox of services, to enable agricultural insurance companies to overcome challenges in three main procedures – underwriting; damage assessment; and contract monitoring, when developing Agricultural Insurance (AgI) services. BEACON is taking advantage of innovations in Earth Observation (EO), weather intelligence and ICT / blockchain technology to deliver tangible innovation in the form of tools and services for the insurance companies enabling them to exploit the untapped market potential of Agricultural Insurance.

The present Deliverable aims to consolidate the strategy of BEACON to define the goals, identify the most efficient means and set a detailed plan for the implementation of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities. To this end the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread BEACON activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences, also becoming the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of BEACON solutions.

1. Introduction

The present Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan was developed within the framework of Task 7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy; WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion. The aim of the deliverable is to consolidate the overall strategy of BEACON, from day one, to define the goals of DEC activities, to identify the most efficient means to achieve them, and decompose them in to a detailed implementation plan. To this end the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread BEACON activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences with a focus also outside EU. The BEACON DEC also aims to set the pace and a number of foreseen activities in order to place the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of BEACON solutions.

The document is outlined in 8 chapters structured to appropriately present the overall BEACON DEC objectives, strategy, target audiences, tools and means, channels and material for an efficient and effective implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities within the project lifespan.

Following an introduction, Chapter 2 describes the overall dissemination strategy, introducing the ecosystem around BEACON, channels to reach out to the target audiences and demonstrates the strategy to ensure active stakeholders engagement.

In Chapter 3, the BEACON communication strategy is elaborated, presenting the BEACON visual identity, communication tools, foreseen activities and material that will be used for the successful implementation of the DEC.

The document continues with Chapter 4 which describes how the DEC will prepare the ground and support the commercialization activities.

Then in Chapter 5 the approach to support the successful deployment of the pilot activities is presented. Liaison and networking activities outlining the approach to link with related EC projects as well as EC and international initiatives for the development of synergies and potential implementation of joint dissemination activities, are described in Chapter 6.

The overall timeline of activities is presented in Chapter 7, with the mechanisms applied for the monitoring of communications and dissemination activities implemented, being elaborated in Chapter 8.

1.1. The BEACON project

The BEACON project aims to develop a commercial auxiliary tool, that will enable insurance companies to exploit the untapped market potential of Agricultural Insurance (AgI). BEACON is taking advantage of innovations in Earth Observation (EO), weather intelligence and ICT / blockchain technology to deliver tangible innovation aspects to an otherwise traditional sector. The Agricultural Insurance (AgI) sector is expanding on a global stage, projected to reach a value to €40 B by 2020. However, the development and provision of agricultural insurance services/products is generally low, characterized by low market penetration and consistent underwriting losses. This is due to certain challenges that AgI providers face in their main three procedures – underwriting; damage assessment; and contract monitoring, when developing AgI services.

BEACON will enable insurance companies to alleviate the effect of weather uncertainty when estimating risk for Agricultural Insurance products, reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes, claims verification and contract handling, and support them design more accurate and personalized contracts. EO data derived by Copernicus Sentinel missions as well as by missions contributing to Copernicus will be used to develop the data products that will act as a complementary source to the information used by insurance companies to design their products and assess natural disasters. Weather intelligence based on data assimilation, numerical weather prediction and ensemble seasonal forecasting will be used to verify the occurrence of a catastrophic weather event and to predict future perils. ICT / blockchain technology will be used for the smart contract service, to provide insurance companies with an automated method for paying out damages to insured parties.

BEACON aspires to be the “tool of choice” of innovative Agricultural Insurance provision services for all actors of the AgI supply chain, from reinsurers to insurers to brokers etc.

1.2. The BEACON project objectives

The main objective of the project is to ensure the product-market fit of BEACON toolbox, for the automated processing and application of earth observation data analytics; meteorological data analytics and forecasting, based on satellite imaging and free and open data.

BEACON toolbox is designed for AgI companies who want to transform their business and empower themselves with EO enabled automated analytics, functions and services on top of remote sensing imagery processing technologies.

Through an **iterative validation process** with Insurance companies/customers BEACON ensures the development of a flexible, value-oriented tool and easy to integrate into current AgI workflow and AgI IT systems toolbox.

Lighthouse Customers and the initial product launch will take place within selected markets and in accordance to the refined timetable.

2. BEACON Dissemination strategy

2.1. Dissemination objectives

The objective of the dissemination strategy is to identify and organize the activities to be performed to maximize the influence/impact of the project and to promote commercial and secondary exploitation routes of the project results. To ensure the widest possible dissemination of the project and to increase its impact and outreach, BEACON dissemination objectives have been set around a four-pillars:

- i. to raise awareness and openly demonstrate clear economic, social, and environmental benefits of utilizing/adopting BEACON solution within the Agri market;
- ii. to reach out and build a sustainable customer base for future expansion;
- iii. to demonstrate the significance and business opportunities deriving from utilizing EO derived data in new products and services within new sectors/markets; and
- iv. to disseminate the respective project outcomes to the widest possible community of potential beneficiaries.

2.2. Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy and activities follow principles and best practices successfully tested by the partners and in line with the EC Guidelines for successful dissemination. The focal point of the BEACON overall Dissemination strategy is the identification and mapping of targeted stakeholders (*whom to disseminate to*) and understanding of their needs and characteristics so as to tailor clear and concise messages (*what to disseminate*) to the different target audiences. This also comes to ensure the use of the most appropriate and efficient dissemination channels and communication tools and drive the development of proper material per target stakeholders (*how to disseminate*). It further defines a time plan (*when to disseminate*), on the basis of which 3 phases are introduced, with specific objectives and target focuses per phase (see Table 6), assisting all project partners in implementing communication

activities and reaching the dissemination and exploitation objectives throughout the project implementation.

Focusing at reaching a wider audience beyond the main targeted stakeholders of the project the DEC will outline liaison and networking activities with other EC projects, initiatives and networks that will further enhance the dissemination range and impact.

2.3. The BEACON ecosystem

The identification of target audiences and of their needs and characteristics, is an essential part of an effective and efficient dissemination strategy. BEACON in general distinguishes two main segments of audiences:

- a. the AgI supply chain actors, including Reinsurance, Insurance Underwriting companies, Claim handlers and Brokers, who represent the core of the BEACON toolbox future customers &
- b. the AgI enablers, including direct and indirect related organization, SME's, research institutions etc. that are directly or indirectly related to the to the provision or support of AgI.

Within BEACON we thus adopt a multi-sectorial and multi-stakeholder approach, expanding our focus at a greater ecosystem of stakeholders (Figure 1) all along the value chain of Agricultural Insurance (AgI) and sectors/technologies linked to the development of the BEACON toolbox. This ecosystem is at first stage consisting of the primary end-users and other expected beneficiaries of BEACON outcomes within the Insurance, Agricultural Industry, Earth Observation, and Blockchain sectors. It further integrates broader segments of stakeholders – European & International initiatives; Scientific Community; Policy makers; General public – that are expected to benefit (both directly and indirectly) from the BEACON outcomes, enhancing the uptake of BEACON technologies and outcomes and creating spillovers to other sectors.

Figure 1. BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders

2.4. BEACON engagement strategy

Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the BEACON targeted audiences is of utmost importance so as to ensure a long-term impact and market-uptake of the project outcomes, with the BEACON consortium composition, allowing access to all the categories of audiences. Direct and indirect access through the partners networks, ensure that the dissemination activities will be effective and successfully achieve high reach and impact KPI's.

The main target audience, Agl companies (already involved in the project as well as additional ones) will be invited to participate and be actively engaged in the project through the “Lighthouse customers” group, being the first users of BEACON and further connect the project to the Agl sector. Their active engagement and interaction within the project aim at generating positive perceptions derived by the recognition of BEACON’s economic, social, and operational benefits. This will not only work as an amplifier in the dissemination of the project outcomes but also will optimally enable the creation of BEACON’s pool of potential future customers.

Engagement with other stakeholders potentially benefiting by the BEACON toolbox, services and outcomes (in and out of the Agl sector), will also be established mainly focusing on raising awareness and diffusing project advancements and results, creating interest and opportunities for further exploitation routes of BEACON’s solutions and outcomes.

In overall, active engagement will support and set the base for the development of the co-creation approach. Reaching out to target audiences and feeding necessary information will prepare the ground for the full iteration cycles that will follow (Task 2.2 Service specifications & BEACON toolbox development roadmap).

2.4.1. Target audiences & interest in BEACON

Targeted dissemination as per BEACON identified target group is realized on the basis of the needs and characteristics of each group and thus enabling us to deliver maximum impact at every step/activity performed in line with the of the dissemination strategy. The Table 2 below, presents the interest each target group will have on the BEACON outcomes and services and how the project aims at engaging with each group.

Table 2. Target audiences & interest in BEACON

Target audience	Interest in BEACON toolbox and services	Objectives	Focus
Agl companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower administrative and operational cost • More precise calculation of risk in agricultural sector • Better monitoring of insurance contracts & handling of claims • Development of new/ personalized Agl products 	Prime BEACON end user during the project implementation and the main potential direct customers post project.	Raise awareness Attract Engage & Interact Diffuse & Promote Create clientele
Agricultural industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support tools for provision of advice and consulting services to farmers • Affordable premium costs for insured farmers • Alert and advisory tools ensuring timely interventions and protect yields 	Intermediate customers of BEACON that will attracted and kept informed all along the project implementation. Targeted dissemination will focus on promoting the use of BEACON toolbox/services in day-to-day farming and consulting activities.	Raise awareness Attract Diffuse & Promote Create clientele
Blockchain sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful use of blockchain technology in Agl services 	Stakeholders within the Blockchain sector will be communication nodes of BEACON activities, with focus to success stories and lessons learnt deriving by the use of blockchain technology in Agl. Potentially exploiting	Raise awareness Diffuse & Promote

2.4.3. AgI Enablers – BEACON Advisory Board

Further to the direct connection with the AgI sector, BEACON is also building bridges with the broader AgI ecosystem through the “AgI Enablers” group. The “AgI enablers” group acts as the BEACON Advisory Board, consisting of external experts directly or indirectly involved within the AgI ecosystem will be established during the project implementation, under the relevant Task 7.3 – Agricultural Insurance Enablers: BEACON Advisory Board, D7.4 – Agricultural Insurance Enablers – Advisory Board report; M5). The “AgI Enablers” scope is two-fold. It is an interactive group of external experts, experts that contribute into the further expansion or formation of AgI schemes coming from public organization/institutions, that will follow the project developments and provide advice and guidance to the partners supporting in a more efficient and effective the implementation of the project activities. At the same time, it will be exploited as a high end dissemination channel for the diffusion of BEACON advancements and outcomes to multiple networks of different segments within the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders and also support active engagement in the project activities.

3. BEACON Communication

3.1. BEACON communication strategy

BEACON is adopting a funneled approach, similar to a marketing funnel, to assure a wide but also targeted communication within the BEACON ecosystem, enable active engagement and achieve efficient dissemination of the project outcomes. Such an approach primarily will focus on generating awareness by conveying key aspects and benefits of the BEACON toolbox and services to the BEACON target audiences and moreover really appeal the core end-users.

Easy to understand visual material are used to make concepts and benefits instantly recognizable for a wide-audience. This aims at cultivating further interest to potential end-users whom will be directed to more detailed information and material about the tools and services. Customized content will be communicated towards specific target audiences, aiming at creating and maintaining an active stakeholders’ ecosystem. Similarly, relevant information will be extracted from project deliverables; interviews with partners, lighthouse customers as well as other target audiences; pilot case studies; industry reports; and will be relayed through the BEACON communication channels to further support active user engagement, aimed at building BEACON clientele base (Figure 2).

Figure 2. BEACON Communication funnel

3.2. Communication tools

BEACON will create and make use of various communication channels/tools, including online, offline as well as interactive (face-to-face) to achieve an efficient and effective interaction with the different stakeholders. Leveraging the experience and the dynamic interaction of BEACON partners with their audiences/engaged stakeholders and customers, BEACON will focus on using specific communications channels that project partners efficiently use for their day-to-day communications with different stakeholders.

3.2.1. BEACON visual identity

3.2.1.1. BEACON logo

The BEACON project logo is presented below in Figure 3. I will be included in all the project dissemination material, documents and communication tools throughout the project lifetime.

Figure 3. BEACON logo (versions)

3.2.2. BEACON Templates

3.2.2.1. BEACON presentation templates

BEACON will be presented in several events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. A presentation template (ppt) has been designed in line with BEACON graphic identity in order to promote the recognition of BEACON.

Figure 4. BEACON presentation template (slide 1)

Additionally, as required per Article 29.4¹ of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of BEACON, will demonstrate the EU emblem along with along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821964.

Furthermore, a project roll-up and posters template have been produced and will be used for presentation at project's own events as well as for external conferences and workshops.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

Figure 5. BEACON roll-up & poster template

3.2.2.2. BEACON deliverables template

The BEACON deliverable template was produced in line with the overall communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writers information.

Figure 6. BEACON deliverables template (cover page)

In the second page a disclaimer that excludes the responsibility of the European Commission for any use that may be made of the information contained in any deliverable as required by Grant Agreement Article 29.5², including a copyright message in order to protect the originality of any produced content within the BEACON project. The document continues with a table with the document's information (Grant Agreement Number, Acronym, Project Full Title, Start Date, Duration, Project URL, Deliverable Number & Name, Work

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

Package Number & Name, Date of Delivery, Nature, Dissemination Level, Lead Beneficiary, Responsible Author and Contributions from) and a table with the document's history.

The fourth page of the template is reserved for the tables of contents and figures. The first three pages of the template remain static, do not change and contain only the information mentioned above.

3.2.3. BEACON online presence

3.2.3.1. BEACON website

The BEACON website – one pager (<http://info.beacon-h2020.com/>) has already been developed and the first version of the website was released on (M4). The BEACON one-pager will be the basis of formulating the BEACON project website aiming to deliver a product-oriented philosophy without neglecting the information of project-side activities.

The BEACON website will contain basic information about the project (about), also introducing the main objectives (features) and services of BEACON. Relevant partners information is also included and an intranet section with limited access to partners only will be developed for intra-consortium communications as well as being a depository of online documents and forms. A dedicated section containing information and links to project deliverables (only public deliverables), and a depository of project's promotional material will be also included. A news section will cover recent news items, published newsletters (including links to download current and archived newsletters), other relevant project publications.

Additionally, a dedicated blog section on the website, the BEACON Content hub, will be hosting articles and posts covering different aspects relating to Agri. The Content hub will be a focal point for the deployment of the Content and Growth Hacking strategy, developed under WP6 aiming to communicate customized content articles to Agri target audiences, enhance their active engagement in BEACON and optimally attract upcoming BEACON customers.

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the BEACON website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

3.2.4. BEACON Social media

BEACON aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing its reach-out to target audiences and broad public and ensure an active interaction with them. To ensure maximum usability and exploit to the most possible BEACON partners' already developed networks in social media, focus has been given to those social media, that BEACON partners have been using regularly and successfully to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

An online questionnaire was created to assess which social media but also other tools and material for communication (and dissemination) BEACON partners are more familiar with and have been already using efficiently and effectively in to their day-to-day communications. On the basis of the feedback received, BEACON project has established (M4) social media account for Twitter, a dedicated Facebook page as well as a project dedicated group on LinkedIn³ .

Figure 7. BEACON social media infographics

Some hashtags, which are being used for the BEACON project, are the following: #BEACON; #insurance; #blockchain; #agtech; #eo; #agi; #Agl_Innovation; #remotesensing; #innovativesolutions; #agribusiness; #h2020; #eu

3.2.4.1. BEACON Facebook page

BEACON's Facebook page will focus at establishing direct communications with target audiences, both in terms of other relevant groups (e.g. Agricultural Insurance Brokers;) as well as individuals, including Agri companies and other audiences' segments. Although considered as main channel for communications of individuals, the BEACON Facebook page will serve for broad communications as well as B2C ones. This is based on the outcomes of the online questionnaire for the use of social media, and on further discussions

³ BEACON h2020 project; <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13699653/>

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

with the project partner Karavias (project coordinator) whose Facebook account is mainly used for day-to-day interaction with its clients (Karavias has great influence on this social media channel in Greece).

Figure 8. BEACON's Facebook page

3.2.4.2. BEACON LinkedIn Group

The BEACON dedicated LinkedIn group will be extensively used for networking purposes, enabling the promotion of BEACON amongst a broad community of professionals within AgI as well as other segments of BEACON's target audiences.

Furthermore, BEACON will seek for interaction with representatives of other relevant groups such as: Agricultural Insurance⁴; Agribusiness and Farm Insurance Specialist (AFIS)⁵, Agricultural Insurance – Academic group⁶, Agriinsurance International⁷, etc., enhancing its outreach and engagement with other target audiences.

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2246387/>

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/5123134/>

⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2669347/>

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4571840/>

Figure 10. BEACON Twitter account

3.3. Newsletter

BEACON e-Newsletters will be composed and published in the project website and social media, but also will be distributed to the consortium members, Lighthouse customers, the “AgI Enablers” as well as networks and direct contacts within the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders. The newsletters will serve as a tool to communicate key updates and developments to the BEACON ecosystem of stakeholders and aiming to keep them informed and engaged.

The content will be incorporating latest developments of the project as well as recent or upcoming dissemination activities; pilot activities deployment and success stories; presentations, workshops and demonstrations; reports, publications and media interest, etc.

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

Figure 11. BEACON Newsletter template

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

Dedicated sections of the BEACON newsletter will focus at the business and commercialization of the BEACON toolbox. In this way value-added content, such as business-related news, trends, analysis, and practical advice pulled from the BEACON Content Hub, pilot success stories, etc. will be fed in continuous way to target audiences.

The newsletter will be published on a 6-months basis, but also ad-hoc for the distribution of important-high priority news and developments. A specific newsletter potential recipients list has already been created and will be populated constantly all along the project implementation. Data Protection Laws will be fully respected, and the newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. At BEACON special attention is paid to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data. Therefore, relevant activities and aspects regarding personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679⁸.

Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BEACON Newsletters and all the collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner's servers. These data will not be accessible from other third-parties. More detailed description of how these data will be collected, stored and handled will be presented in the respective deliverables (D1.3 – Data Management Plan).

In order to achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, the BEACON partners will be encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

A specific option for subscription to the list of newsletter recipients, has been included on the BEACON in two parts of the website.

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

Figure 12. Subscription to BEACON newsletters (call to action button-Head)

Figure 13 Subscription to BEACON newsletters (call to action button-footer)

3.4. BEACON promotional material

3.4.1. Project fiche – BEACON One pager

A short project fiche (Figure 10) will be used for ice-breaking communications with interested stakeholders, providing them with a first view on the BEACON project. The project fiche structure and content will be adapted to the needs of any communications with different stakeholders segments, highlighting relevant to each segment information. Incorporated with background information and/or customized content based on the project developments, the project fiche together with BEACON press releases, will be circulated to specialized media channels (as well as mass media) and journalists enhancing the project outreach.

Figure 14. BEACON one pager

3.4.2. BEACON Project Brochure & Factsheets

The BEACON project will produce a brochure and a set of different factsheets to enhance the promotion of the BEACON tools and services. These printed promotional materials will be distributed at different project related and other events that BEACON partners will be present, as well as in meetings and other project promotional activities.

Figure 15. BEACON Brochure

3.4.3. Press releases

Press releases about the BEACON project activities and developments will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project focusing at both broad audiences and more specific stakeholders. Apart from specific project activities the topics covered may include opinions/interviews of experts within and out of the partner organizations, attracting media attention on relevant topics. A continuous cooperation with press and media will be promoted by all BEACON partners. All press releases will be also be available on the BEACON project website as well as social media channels.

Figure 16. BEACON press release

3.5. Conferences and events

BEACON partners will take part in local (national), EU and international level conferences, industrial fairs events and exhibitions in order to raise awareness around the BEACON activities and expected results and disseminate the relevant developments and outcomes. Partners will focus to promote BEACON in key industry events which attract high number of players across the sectors of interest (Agl, Agricultural Risk Management, EO, Blockchain, etc.), aiming to maximize the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders. Additionally attending relevant event it will also benefit BEACON by having continuous updates about specific AgI market aspects so to address them in to BEACON exploitation plans.

The Table 4 below provides a list of indicative relevant upcoming events in which presentation of BEACON will be aimed. This list will be continuously updated and extended, and further communicated with all BEACON partners to plan participations in upcoming events. The dissemination through these events will be customized on the basis of the BEACON main target audience (Agl companies) but also ensuring wide dissemination across sectors and stakeholders.

Table 4. List of BEACON relevant events & conferences

Events/Conferences	Date/location
86 th International Agricultural Fair	11 May, 2019 Novi Sad, Serbia
Connected Insurance Europe 2019	15 May, 2019 Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Agro-insurance consolidation workshop	16 May 2019, Milan, Italy
The International Insurance – Reinsurance Forum	19 May, 2019 Sinaia, Romania
11 th International Insurance conference	23 May, 2019 Bucharest, Romania
Crypto Valley Conference on Blockchain Technology	24 June, 2019 Zug, Switzerland
Digital Insurance Agenda	26 June, 2019 Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Earth Observation ϕ -week	9 September, 2019 Frascati (Rome), Italy
Insurance 3.0	3 October, 2019 London, United Kingdom
35 th International Association of Agricultural Production Insurers Congress	6-9 October, 2019 Bordeaux, France
InsurTech Summit International	10 October, 2019 Paris, France
Baden-Baden XPRIMM Reception 10th Edition	21 October 2019 Baden-Baden, Germany
ICARMCI 2019 : International Conference on Agricultural Risk Management and Crop Insurance	9-10 December, 2019 London, United Kingdom
28th Agrotica	30 January, 2020 Thessaloniki, Greece
General Assembly 2020 of the European Geosciences Union (EGU)	5 March, 2010 Vienna, Austria

3.6. Publications

Technical and Business-wise publications will be also exploited. BEACON aims to exploit such channels and perform targeted dissemination towards business and technical oriented audiences, through publications at relevant business journals and magazines. It is expected that 5 publications will be produced during the project lifespan enhancing the BEACON outcomes dissemination. Some relevant local and international business journals are the following: Private insurance; Insurance Daily; Insurance Forum; Insurance world; EKO list; Business Perceptiveness; Humble; etc.

Although, Scientific publications are not the primary focus of BEACON, such publications may be performed in parallel to the pilot implementations if deemed necessary.

3.7. Early communication activities

BEACON aiming at being extrovert from the very beginning of the project start. Relevant activity is presented here below.

The first press release (Figure 16) was published at Greek mass media after the kick-off of the project by the project coordinator Karavias Underwriting Agency⁹.

⁹ Online version can be found at: <http://www.kathimerini.gr/1012692/article/oikonomia/epixeirhseis/asfalistika-symvolaia-gia-ka8e-xwrafi-3exwrista-mesw-toy-beacon>

Figure 17. BEACON project kick-off press release

Additionally, BEACON has been already presented in the following events:

- April, 7-12, 2019 Vienna, Austria. European Geoscience Union (EGU), General Assembly; Oral presentation by UPM.
- April 10-12, 2019 Mexico. Munich RE - "Agro Future Lab"; Remote presentation from ETHERISC
- March 6-7, 2019 Munich, Germany. ARA Symposium 2019 - Agricultural Insurance in a Changing Climate; Oral presentation by AgroApps.

The above partners were invited to participate presenting their (commercial) activity within the scope of the conferences/events and BEACON was included in their overall presentation.

4. Linking BEACON DEC with commercialization

BEACON project is steered towards the market and the policy covering the provision of AgI. Starting from a complementary consortium consisting of experienced multi-sector partners (academic, technical, business and institutional actors) and with a strong industry participation, both from partners side as well as lighthouse customers side; BEACON is continuously in the look out to further engage direct and indirect AgI actors to its activities. The DEC is playing a key role in this process, formulating the starting point of every communication-dissemination and early engagement activity, ensuring a quick pass from communication to involvement.

Thus, the DEC approach starts at the very beginning, by raising awareness, linking and promoting uptake of EO data and technologies by industry through focused materials targeting to generate lead and support this aim (insights, videos, graphic elements, etc.). Furthermore, it moves towards more "attractive and engaging activities" such as presentation and experience-based activities, where practical examples, pilot success stories and business generated cases are used to force understanding and further establish the added value of BEACON.

The overall aim remains throughout this process, to reach, to communicate and disseminate generated value, to grow the reach of the project, attract and involve more end-users, improve project results, and facilitate end-user uptake after completion of the project.

The DEC and Commercialization go hand with hand throughout the BEACON project, and complement one another, on a step by step basis. Such joining of forces represents a special marketing strategy, which will emphasize performances of both teams, DEC and growth hacking (D6.1 Content and Growth Hacking strategy). Namely, DEC will help the growth hacking team becoming more visible in the virtual world through continual relationship with targeted audiences. Vice versa, growth hacking is supporting the DEC in spreading the content virally. In this way, the developed synergy will create substantial improvements and multiplier effect for BEACON Toolbox and optimally enable its uptake, which is the overall goal of both teams.

5. Diffusion through tangible results

5.1. DEC plan and Pilots deployment

BEACON will build on top of “stories made” with our Lighthouse Customers. BEACON will exploit and built on top of BEACON pilot activities, turning outcomes into success stories. Adopting a funneled approach, pilot activities and experiences, case studies, interviews with partners, Lighthouse customers and other involved actors, will be transformed in to success stories that will be feeding the communications to BEACON’s target audiences, aiming to ensure that project progress and pilot results reach the AgI sector actors. The BEACON success stories will be formed either as written or video testimonials, aiming at showcasing the value of the BEACON toolbox and services and become a proof of experience for additional target audiences. “AgI enablers” AB group will also be exploited to structure and disseminate similar successful paradigms.

6. Liaison and networking activities

In order to enhance the visibility of BEACON and to ensure maximum attractiveness and engagement of AgI and relevant actors, a series of liaison and networking meetings will be organized/attended within the project life span. Primarily this activity will have a business focus, aiming at further connecting BEACON with Lighthouse customers; AgI target stakeholders and other end users, to optimally start building its potential clientele. These activities will be implemented in conjunction with activities under WP6 – BEACON Commercialization Playbook and Growth Hacking.

Beyond the business focus, liaison and networking activities will seek for collaborations and establish dialogue with different EU/International projects and initiatives, as well as relevant networks and organizations relating to BEACON’s scope and activities. This will be an on-going activity that will enable exchange of views and potential development of synergies.

The following table presents the two approaches followed by BEACON to successfully gauge potential customer interest, support active engagement, and seek for further collaborations.

7. Timeline of activities

The overall DEC plan will be deployed in 3 main phases as presented in the below Table 4. Each phase is defined with clear objectives to be achieved and the focus so as to serve the efficient implementation of the DEC strategy.

Table 6. DEC deployment phases

Phase	Months	Objective	Intensity	Focus
I	1 – 37	This phase will have an approach-oriented content, for the establishment of the ecosystem of stakeholders, aiming to ensure wide project presentation on objectives, expected results & promote pilots’ activities. Raising awareness is a continuous activity that will be deployed all along the project lifespan.	Medium	Reach out & Raise awareness
II	18 - 25	During the second phase the aim is to create a more targeted awareness regarding BEACON. Advancements and techniques implemented for overcoming known challenges in the AgI sector and their added value towards specific stakeholders and communities within the BEACON ecosystem, will be transposed in to storytelling and key messages to attract active engagement of end users. Along with the deployment of pilot cases, further promotional activities will focus at triggering the interest of target audiences and also mobilize the Lighthouse customers to actively connect with the BEACON toolbox and get engaged in relevant project activities.	High	Attract - Engage - Interact
III	25-37	This last phase will focus at promoting concrete BEACON results to its key stakeholders, aiming at the creation of BEACON customer base, establishing a positive word of mouth and building upon pilot success stories and Lighthouse customers feedback. All activities during the 3 rd phase will focus on attracting and delivering more users-actors to the BEACON toolbox, to establish mutual beneficial synergies with AgI actors and strengthen further commercial links with them.	High	Diffuse & Promote

8. Monitoring of communication and dissemination activities

In order to achieve the successful implementation of Communication and Dissemination activities, and fulfillment of the relevant objectives, a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation. The monitoring will be performed internally on a trimestral basis and will be officially reported in the relevant Deliverables D7.2 BEACON promotional activities and engagement reports I and II on M17 and 37 respectively. Regular monitoring will allow the identification of possible risks and deviations from the DEC objectives and performance indicators, and the timely planning of any necessary corrections actions to address potential implementation problems. Such an approach will improve the overall performance of the relevant activities and enable a more efficient evaluation.

An online form has been created for reporting all DEC activities partners' perform. The form is be available to all partners via the Intranet section of the BEACON project website, and all reported activity will be stored at the projects' documents repository (Dropbox file). All activity reported will be incorporated in the trimestral internal reporting and relevant project deliverables (as above mentioned).

Online presence of BEACON will be monitored using specific analytics monitoring software i.e. Google analytics and relevant social media analytics too.

Table 7 below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which will be used to evaluate the success of the project's actions.

Table 7. Key performance indicators

Key Performance indicators	Target value	Means of verification
Project website pageviews	60.000	Google analytics
Social media followers	6.000	Social media analytics
Sector-specific newsletters	10	Project reporting
Newsletter subscribers	2.000	Email records (Mailchimp)
Blog posts	100	Project reporting
Videos released	30	Project reporting
PR articles published in reg-nat-EU press	200	Project reporting
Publications in business journals	5	Project reporting
Distributed printed material	5.000	Project reporting
Presentations in forums, workshops relevant to project results	10	Project reporting
Meetings (Agl; EO; Farmers Organisations; Institutions (EU/Internat.))	35	Project reporting

Informal person-to-person meetings with relevant national stakeholders	85	Project reporting
--	----	-------------------

9. References

- Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement, Version 5.1 December 2018. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

